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Effectiveness of the Planning Facilitation program for the prevention of reading comprehension difficulties

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Abstract:

The aim of the study is to analyze the role of PASS cognitive processes in the improvement of reading comprehension within a group of students whose reading performance was beginning to differ from their classmates with whom they had started their primary schooling. The presence of this achievement difficulty in reading comprehension was observed at the beginning of the third year of primary education. The group of students at risk of reading comprehension difficulties ($n = 8$) underwent training, while their classmates acted as a control group. The total number of students in the classroom was 30. The Reading Comprehension Assessment test, the four scales of the Cognitive Assessment System Battery (Planning, Attention, Simultaneous, and Successive), and the Reading Awareness Scale were used for the evaluation of the students. The reading comprehension program was implemented using the Planning Facilitation method. The results showed an improvement in the care process that was manifested in the posttest and planning measure, which remained active from the premeasure to the follow-up. At this moment of the measurement, the improvement of the simultaneous processing with a great activity of reading comprehension and awareness was manifested. Reading comprehension and awareness improved significantly in the post measure and increased in the follow-up measure with simultaneous processing. These results are interpreted in the sense that the Planning Facilitation program has a specific effect on the processes of knowledge (reading awareness) and metacognitive control (planning and attention), as well as on the simultaneous cognitive process and on the transfer of these to reading comprehension. Planning activates the functioning of simultaneous processing and its control, and once the cognitive weakness of simultaneous disappears, reading comprehension is performed competently.

Keywords: Planning facilitation, metacognition, metacognitive instruction, reading comprehension, PASS theory.

Effectiveness of the Planning Facilitation program for the prevention of reading comprehension difficulties

INTRODUCTION

This study aims to analyze the role of PASS processes in the learning of reading comprehension. Deaño et al. (2019) reported that training in reading comprehension strategies through Planning Facilitation improved comprehension and reading awareness. An unexpected result was the increase in planning scores of the intervention group. This change occurred because the pretest scores of the intervention group were in the normative average and did not differ from the control group. Previous studies with Planning Facilitation (Haddad et al., 2003; Naglieri & Gottling, 1997; Naglieri & Johnson, 2000), as well as with reflective verbalization (Cormier et al., 1990; Kar et al., 1993), indicated that increases in planning scores occur when they are below the normative average. Planning, on the other hand, controls the strategies used in learning reading comprehension as understood by the PASS theory, integrating information through simultaneous processing. Planning could strive to improve its control over how concurrent processing works and become more effective in doing so. These two matches (average planning and the need for improvement of simultaneous processing) could have contributed to the increase in the score of both. Consequently, the main purpose of the current study is establishing whether planning is improved by increasing the weakened functioning of simultaneous processing and reading comprehension.

The comprehension process requires the students to use strategies to be able to deal effectively with the text. Strategies are intentional cognitive processes (Alexander et al., 1998). A reading strategy is a set of actions sequenced in a deliberate way aiming at understanding the meaning of the text. Reading also requires higher-order skills, such as semantics and inferential (Gutiérrez-Fresneda & Del Olmo, 2019). The semantic process requires to integrate ideas from the sentences with each other with the reader's previous knowledge about the sentence to build the mental or situational model (Van den Broek, 2010). The inferences (Perfetti, 2010; Perfetti et al., 2005) facilitate the reading comprehension of the text-text and text-previous knowledge relationships, favoring the necessary mental

representation of a more elaborate global structure (Dole et al., 2009). Understanding the meaning of the essential element for reading (Nation & Norbury, 2005) is supported by the simultaneous cognitive process, which underlies reading comprehension (Georgiou & Das, 2014). Simultaneous processing integrates separate elements in an interrelated set using both verbal and non-verbal content (Georgiou & Das, 2014), performs a synthesis, and reduces it to a global unit of information (Das et al., 1994). Finally, reading also requires metacognitive knowledge and control skills that contribute to good comprehension (Carretti et al., 2014; Das & Georgiou, 2016; Das & Misra, 2015; Hulme & Snowling, 2009; Kostons & Van der Werf, 2015).

Metacognitive activity depends on the ability to evaluate, monitor, and influence one's own cognitive processes (Shimamura, 2000) and involves the interaction between the skills of representation, prediction, execution, and regulation of a plan (Das, 1998; Das et al., 1996; Das & Misra, 2015). The regulation of reading comprehension implies that during the execution of the reading activity aimed at the goal, the interferences must be resisted, and the task monitored, responding to the feedback of the action that requires a change in strategy (Das & Misra, 2015).

The risk of experiencing reading difficulties requires considering the factors involved in reading comprehension. Several authors have highlighted inferences among these skills, together with the monitoring of understanding and sensitivity to the structure of the story (Perfetti, 2010; Perfetti et al., 2005), which are usually considered higher-order skills. The inferences allow the reader to identify the relationships between the parts of the text and relate it to their previous knowledge; that is, they are based on both knowledge of language and knowledge of the world (Dole et al., 2009; León, 2004; Van den Broek, 2010). Inferential skills, around the age of 8, are presented as one of the factors that determine textual comprehension (León, 2004). People with a reading deficit have difficulties with inferences to build an integrated and coherent representation of the text, and they demonstrate a lower ability to make cohesive and elaborative inferences (Cain & Oakhill, 2011). A reading comprehension difficulty can present with a cognitive weakness in the simultaneous

process that underlies it. This implies a dysfunction to integrate the information in a global idea. Studies reveal that a weakness in simultaneous processing in students is related to reading comprehension difficulties (Das et al., 1994; Mahapatra, 2015) and would indicate difficulty in relating the words of a sentence to obtain their meaning and in integrating words in phrases or ideas and those ideas in other main ones (Das et al., 1994).

Through the instructional procedure of Planning Facilitation, Naglieri and Gottling (1997) and Naglieri and Johnson (2000) found that weaker students in planning improved substantially more in mathematical calculation than those who had no weakness in planning. Haddad et al. (2003) evaluated whether an instruction designed to improve planning would have a differential benefit on reading comprehension, according to the PASS characteristics of each student. The results showed that students with a cognitive weakness in planning benefited substantially from an intervention designed to facilitate planning. The effectiveness of the Planning Facilitation intervention in students with difficulty in informed planning for academic content (arithmetic, reading fluency, and reading accuracy; Naglieri & Gottling, 1997; Naglieri & Johnson, 2000) and non-academic content (Cormier et al., 1990; Kar et al., 1993) suggests that the intervention method could be applicable to a variety of curricular areas, including reading (Haddad et al., 2003).

Objectives and hypotheses

The general objective is to analyze the role of the PASS processes in students starting to develop reading comprehension difficulties with respect to their peers.

1. The first objective is to show the effects of the Planning Facilitation program on the cognitive (Simultaneous) and metacognitive processes of knowledge (Reading Awareness) and control (Planning and Attention) that underlie reading comprehension. It is expected that the intervention group will show a significant increase in their scores on the Simultaneous Scales of Reading Awareness (ESCOLA) and control of cognitive activity (Planning and Attention) because of the intervention, and there will be no statistically significant differences in their scores in the posttest and follow-up measure with respect to the control group.

2. The second objective is to show the transference effects of the program on reading comprehension. The intervention group is expected to show a significant increase in their scores on the Reading Comprehension

Assessment (ACL) because of the transfer effects of the program, and there will be no statistically significant differences in their scores in the posttest and follow-up measure of the intervention group compared to the control group.

METHODOLOGY

Participants

A quasi-experimental study made up of 30 students from a third-grade classroom of primary education was carried out. The intervention group was made up of 8 students who were at risk for reading comprehension problems and a comparison group consisted of the 22 students in the classroom who were not at risk. By sex, 13 were girls and 17 were boys. No significant differences were found by sex and group ($\chi^2(1) = 0.454$; $p = 0.501$). They were students of urban origin. The educational level of the parents was secondary for the most part, and their annual income is at the average economic level. The sample had homogeneous characteristics in terms of social, economic, and cultural variables. Sample was also homogeneous in her successive cognitive processing scores [$F(1, 29) = 0.871$, $p = 0.359$] and planning [$F(1, 29) = 0.927$, $p = 0.344$].

The groups were different in their simultaneous processing scores [$F(1, 29) = 12.991$, $p = 0.001$]. They also varied regarding attention [$F(1, 29) = 7.249$, $p = 0.009$]; reading awareness [$F(1, 29) = 4.037$, $p = 0.047$], and reading comprehension [$F(1, 29) = 9.501$, $p = 0.005$]. Scores were higher in the comparison group.

Instruments

Pretest/posttest and follow-up evaluation

Specific effects

Das Battery and Naglieri: Cognitive Assessment System (D.N: CAS; Naglieri & Das, 1997) was administered for the measurement of cognitive processes. The Planning Scale consists of three subtests designed to measure the planning or cognitive process involved in executive functioning, that is, determining, selecting, and using efficient solutions. The Attention Scale is measured through three subtests in which the participant is required to resist distraction and maintain properly directed attention to complete specific tasks.

The Simultaneous Scale measures simultaneous processing, which involves the interrelation of component parts to arrive at a correct solution. The three tasks designed

for the Simultaneous Scale require verbal and non-verbal synthesis of separate components in an organized group. (i) Non-Verbal Matrices were designed using the standard progressive matrix format. Interrelated geometric shapes are presented to the participant to establish relationships and then choose the multiple-choice selection that correctly completes the analogy shown. (ii) Verbal-Spatial Relationships require the individual to answer a question that describes the spatial relationships of a specific drawing that is presented with five distracting drawings. (iii) Memory of Figures is the final simultaneous task presented to the participant. The examinee is shown a geometric figure for five seconds. The participant is required to find and trace that figure by heart in a more complex drawing. The tasks on the Successive Scale require the participant to organize the stimuli in an explicit serial order. The result is a chain progression with elements that are only related to the previous element. This scale also includes three subtests.

The Reading Awareness Scale (ESCOLA; Puente et al., 2009) was also administered in its long version of 56 items, in approximately 40 minutes. The scale assesses the planning, supervision, and evaluation processes that children from 8 to 13 years of age carry out when faced with reading situations posed as dilemmas. The processes described are evaluated according to three variables: person, task, and text. The scale allows, through direct scoring, to obtain the corresponding percentile based on the age and course of the subjects. Its reliability index calculated using Cronbach's alpha is 0.81.

Transferrential effects on reading comprehension

The Reading Comprehension Assessment (ACL) test by Català et al. (2001) was applied. The ACL consists of six tests, corresponding to each of the six courses of primary education. They are aimed at assessing reading comprehension in a broad way, with narrative, expository, poetic texts, interpretation of a graph, and interpretation of data. These tests collect information on four relevant dimensions of reading comprehension: literal, reorganizational, inferential, and critical. For grade 3 of primary education, the ACL-3 was used. The items for this grade are presented in a format of short texts that are attractive and of interest for the age of the students. The reliability of the test for the third year of primary education, calculated using the KR-20, is 0.80.

Intervention procedure

The Intervention Program carried out is based on the texts of the ACL test –used to answer questions asked to the students about each of the texts at a certain level. The program started with the lower-level texts, starting at ACL-2, followed by texts from ACL-1, and concluded with ACL-4 and ACL-5. The ACL-3 was not used because it was part of the measurement instruments. The program consists of eight to ten texts per level.

The Intervention Procedure was carried out in a small group system. Each group was made up of 4 participants. The text reading tasks were implemented using the Planning Facilitation method, which consists of three moments. Moment 1: The teacher gives the students a text with the five questions they must answer individually, having a total of ten minutes to read it. Moment 2: with the questions answered by student showing, the teacher starts a debate by asking questions such as, “What is it about?” “What are we being told and what is the purpose of the question?” “What idea can be formulated?” “How did you do it?” “Why did you do it this way?” “How will you do it next time?” and “Could you have done it differently?” (Das, 1998, p. 159). The teacher does not have to exhaust the repertoire of questions about the chosen text or ask the questions only to one student. The text serves as an excuse for dialogue. If this occurs with the initiative of the students, the teacher stops asking, if the initiative fades or if some response situation is not focused due to lack of the most pertinent question, they continue asking. After ten minutes, the discussion is over. Moment 3: The teacher collects the covered sheets of all the students and gives others the same text and questions for them to solve in ten minutes.

The time for the completion of a text was half an hour per session, twice a week and twice with each group. For each intervention group, the number of texts used was 24, with 2 sessions per week.

Results

Design and data analysis

A pre/intervention/post/follow-up design was used, contrasting the intervention and comparison groups in each measure, and implementing a repeated measures multivariate analysis of variance (MANOVA) for the cognitive processes (Planning, Attention, Simultaneous,

Successive, Scale Complete; DN: CAS) and reading [reading comprehension (ACL), reading awareness (ESCOLA)].

Effect on cognitive processes

In the results obtained, a main effect of the measure on cognitive processes was not obtained [F (5.64, 236.925) = 0.257, $p = 0.950$, $\eta^2_{parcial} = 0.006$]. Pairwise comparisons of mean scores did indicate significant variations in median size from pretest to follow-up in planning [F (2, 84) = 5.138, $p = 0.008$, $\eta^2_{parcial} = 0.109$; $\Delta M = 10.912$, $p = 0.007$], simultaneous [F (2, 84) = 5.367, $p = 0.006$, $\eta^2_{parcial} = 0.113$; $\Delta M = 11.182$, $p = 0.005$], attention [F (2, 84) = 3.448, $p = 0.036$, $\eta^2_{parcial} = 0.076$; $\Delta M = 9.116$, $p = 0.040$], and successively [F (2, 84) = 4.085, $p = 0.020$, $\eta^2_{parcial} = 0.089$; $\Delta M = 9.696$, $p = 0.016$]. On the full scale, the scores significantly increased statistically and with a large effect size from the pretest to the posttest measurement [F (2, 84) = 9.147, $p < 0.001$, $\eta^2_{parcial} = 0.179$; $\Delta M = 9.670$, $p = 0.009$] and from the pretest to follow-up measure [F (2, 84) = 9.147, $p < 0.001$, $\eta^2_{parcial} = 0.179$; $\Delta M = 13.097$, $p < 0.001$].

The main effect of group medium size on cognitive processes was obtained [F (2.82, 236.925) = 9.546, $p < 0.001$, $\eta^2_{parcial} = 0.102$]. The comparison group showed higher overall mean scores than the simultaneous processing intervention [F (1, 84) = 33.976, $p < 0.001$, $\eta^2_{parcial} = 0.288$; $\Delta M = 16.295$, $p < 0.001$] and on the full scale [F (1, 84) = 11.877, $p = 0.001$, $\eta^2_{parcial} = 0.124$; $\Delta M = 8.937$, $p = 0.001$].

There was no significant interaction of the measure by group for cognitive processes [F (5.64, 236.925) = 1.150, $p = 0.329$, $\eta^2_{parcial} = 0.027$], but there were significant oscillations of the mean scores in processes for groups from one measure to another. Considering the initial differences between groups in the scales of simultaneous, attention, and the full scale, their performance in the latter two after the intervention were equal. In the follow-up measure, the intervention group equaled its mean scores to that of the comparison in simultaneous processing; in this measure, both groups were also equal in the mean scores of all cognitive processes and of the full scale.

The evolution shown by each group showed that the intervention group obtained a significant median size gain in the posttest measure with respect to the pretest in attention [F (2.84) = 5.302, $p = 0.007$, $\eta^2_{parcial} = 0.112$; $\Delta M = 15.625$, $p = 0.040$] and large in full scale [F (2.84) = 6.753, $p = 0.002$, $\eta^2_{parcial} = 0.139$; $\Delta M = 13.750$, $p = 0.040$]. It also obtained a significant gain in the medium size from

pretest to follow-up in planning [F (2, 84) = 4.104, $p = 0.020$, $\eta^2_{parcial} = 0.089$; $\Delta M = 16.704$, $p = 0.019$], simultaneous [F (2, 84) = 3.508, $p = 0.034$, $\eta^2_{parcial} = 0.077$; $\Delta M = 15.125$, $p = 0.035$], and attention [F (2, 84) = 5.302, $p = 0.007$, $\eta^2_{parcial} = 0.139$; $\Delta M = 18.771$, $p = 0.009$], and large in size on the full scale [F (2, 84) = 6.753, $p = 0.002$, $\eta^2_{parcial} = 0.139$; $\Delta M = 19.442$, $p = 0.002$].

The comparison group did not have a significant increase in the mean score in any of the cognitive processes or in the full scale from one measure to another.

Effects on reading awareness

The results obtained showed the main effect of the measure on reading awareness. In the posttest and follow-up measures with respect to the pretest, there was a significant increase in the large size of the mean reading awareness scores [Mpre = 62.17, Mpos = 76.32, Mfollow-up = 79.13; F (2.84) = 23.244, $p < 0.001$, $\eta^2_{parcial} = 0.356$].

There was no main group effect on reading awareness measures. Comparisons between the groups, considering the initial differences of the groups in the variables analyzed, showed in the posttest measure that they were equal in their performance in reading awareness and remained the same for both groups in the follow-up measure. There was also no significant interaction of the measure by group for reading awareness.

The evolution of each group showed that the intervention group obtained a significant gain of large size in the post and follow-up measures with respect to the pretest in reading awareness [$\Delta M_{pos} = 16,750$, $p = 0.001$; $\Delta M_{follow-up} = 19.438$, $p < 0.001$; F (2.84) = 10.642, $p < 0.001$, $\eta^2_{parcial} = .202$]. The comparison group significantly increased their mean scores in reading awareness in the post-test measure ($\Delta M = 11.545$, $p < 0.001$) and in follow-up ($\Delta M = 14.477$, $p < 0.001$) with a large effect size [F (2.84) = 15.454, $p < 0.001$, $\eta^2_{parcial} = 0.269$].

Effects on reading comprehension

The results obtained showed the main effect of the measure on reading [F (2.84) = 20.049, $p < 0.001$, $\eta^2_{parcial} = 0.323$]. In the posttest and follow-up measurements with respect to the pretest, there was a significant increase in the large size of the mean reading comprehension scores [Mpre = 4.36, Mpos = 5.58, Mfollow-up = 6.17; F (2.84) = 6.905, $p = 0.002$, $\eta^2_{parcial} = 0.141$]. There was no group main effect on reading measures [F (1.84) = 2.134, $p = 0.148$, $\eta^2_{parcial} = 0.025$]. Initial differences were shown in the comparison of means in the groups in the posttest, reaching the same level

in their comprehension performance, which was maintained in the follow-up measure. There was also no significant interaction of the group measure for reading comprehension [$F(2, 84) = 0.349, p = 0.707, \eta^2_{\text{partial}} = 0.008$]. The evolution of each group showed that the intervention group obtained a significant gain in reading comprehension in the improvement of the mean score in the follow-up ($\Delta M = 2,700, p = 0.006$) with respect to the pretest of medium size [$F(2.84) = 5.234, p = 0.007, \eta^2_{\text{parcial}} = 0.111$].

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

As expected, the intervention group showed a significant increase in their scores in ESCOLA in the posttest measure, as it did in attention. Planning increased its scores significantly from pretest to follow-up. The Simultaneous showed a significant score increase in the follow-up measure. The planning process in which the groups were equal improved significantly in the intervention throughout the measures, outperforming its comparison group, which did not experience differences in their scores in cognitive processes. The changes experienced by the intervention group made it possible to match their functioning in the various cognitive and metacognitive processes to the control group or even improve it. These improvements are due to the specific effect of the intervention program followed.

Regarding the second objective, the intervention group showed a significant increase in their ACL scores, which were equal in the posttest measure and increased in the follow-up. The control group did not vary in their scores.

These results are consistent with those obtained by other authors in studies on planning and training verbalization (Cormier et al., 1990; Haddad et al., 2003; Kar et al., 1993; Naglieri & Gottling, 1995, 1997; Naglieri & Johnson, 2000). Verbalization, used as a basis in the Planning Facilitation program, has helped students to develop their strategies to carry out the reading activity with a purpose and regulate it through their own language (Cormier et al., 1990). Verbalization promotes the recognition and identification of the processing aspects of the task, the anticipation of the limitations inherent in its solution, and the development of awareness. Verbalization promotes the recognition and identification of the processing aspects of the task, the anticipation of the limitations inherent to its solution, and the development of task resolution awareness (Kar et al., 1993).

Verbalization, as part of explicit metacognition, made it possible to share one's experiences with others, promoting reflective discussion (Das & Misra, 2015). The group discussion on the resolution of the tasks carried out with the program, without direct instruction from the teacher, has promoted the improvement of reading awareness and comprehension, helping students to adjust their question strategies to better understand the text, and read and execute it more flexibly, inhibiting irrelevant responses (Das & Misra, 2015). The instruction with the program favored the students' analysis of self-supervision and self-correction of the task (Cormier et al., 1990).

Reading awareness improved with the performance of the tasks directed and guided by the mediated intervention and the collaboration of the students to learn. Considering the results in the different moments of the measurement, the students become aware of the use of the strategies for later using them, controlling them progressively. The awareness of use and progressive control of the task execution seem to be responsible for the improvement of the simultaneous process, which is required to integrate and use the information, control the comprehension task and its improvement, and match its comprehension performance to that of the control group. Both awareness and reading comprehension become more efficient in the follow-up measure when simultaneous processing increases its performance. The cognitive activity of reading comprehension is then presented and regulated by the underlying metacognitive knowledge and control (Das & Misra, 2015) that needs to be activated to make such activities possible (Kostons & Van der Werf, 2015).

The results obtained in this study supplement those of Haddad et al. (2003) in various ways. The third level of primary education is the right time for dealing with incipient reading learning difficulties that have not manifested in previous courses, and that arise from the need for a change in cognitive activity to engage with reading information. Planning Facilitation not only benefits those who have planning difficulties, but also increases planning in those who typically need it for improving their cognitive control, changing the way of working with successive processing in relation to simultaneous processing. Reading awareness can be increased in the third year of primary education and its manifestation becomes evident, maintained, and transferred to the improvement, executive, and control of reading tasks. The follow-up measure seems to become essential in this type of study to show the manifestation of strategies progressively discovered by the

students themselves, which are then maintained and transferred to new learning situations.

This study has limitations that should be resolved in future research. This is a study with an intentional sample to attend to a specific situation in a classroom with students at risk of learning difficulties and in which the metacognitive instruction was carried out with subjects who needed an educational response. This has caused a second limitation, which is the assignment of participants to groups. On the other hand, the groups are not balanced in their number and the total sample needs to be increased. The typical comparison group has also improved its reading comprehension and reading awareness scores. This has predictably concealed the interactive effect of the measure by group, reducing the importance of the improvement obtained by the intervention group until it equals the comparison group. However, it allows for an attempt to exemplify ways of responding to the needs of students at risk of experiencing reading difficulties.

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